

MANAGEMENT STYLE AND CLASSROOM ENGAGEMENT OF TEACHERS: KEY VARIABLES OF JOB COMMITMENT AND ATTACHMENT

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ABSTRACT

The main objective of this study was to find out the relationship of teacher's management style and classroom engagement to teacher's job commitment and attachment in the District of Tiaong. The respondents of the study composed of one hundred (100) elementary school teachers in the District of Tiaong, Division of Quezon. Survey questionnaire was the main instrument in gathering the data. The study revealed the following findings: Teachers' perception on management style in classroom in terms of authoritative is much practiced while fairly practiced in terms of authoritarian, permissive, and indulgent. The level of teachers' classroom engagement in terms of cognitive, emotional, and social engagement is highly engaged. Teachers are "highly committed" to job commitment in terms of affective commitment, continuance commitment, and normative commitment. Teachers' job attachment or attachment with students in terms of closeness with students is highly attached and attached in terms of conflict with students. Teacher's management styles and level of engagement in the classroom have no significant relationship with teacher's job commitment and job attachment. The findings of the study led to the conclusion that the hypothesis stating that there is no significant relationship between teachers' job commitment and attachment with teachers' management style and classroom engagement is accepted. In the light of the findings and conclusions derived from this investigation, the researcher recommends the following: It may be recommended to determine the degree of stress and burnout among teachers which is caused by the employment of management style and level of classroom engagement. It may also be recommended to conduct study on teacher's degree of employment of different management styles to certain subject since there is no definite or standard management style used in all areas of teaching.

Keywords: Management Style, Classroom Engagement, Job Commitment, Job Attachment